

Original Article

STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN BUSINESS MATHEMATICS AMONG BUSINESS EDUCATION STUDENTS OF STATE-OWNED UNIVERSITIES IN RIVERS STATE.

Dr. Jim, Ernest Uwaneze and Echezona, Christy Ihunda

^{1,2}Department of Business Education, Rivers State University Nkpolu-Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt, Rivers State.
[ernestjim100@gmail.com/](mailto:ernestjim100@gmail.com)
ernest.jim@ust.edu.ng
(08063908394)
christyechezona77@gmail.com
(08038692543)
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Abstract

This study determined suitable strategies for improving academic performance in business mathematics among business education students in Rivers State owned universities. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. Population of the study consisted of all 57 business educators from the two state-owned universities in the state, namely; Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port-Harcourt. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was small and manageable structured questionnaire with five-point scale was the instrument for data collection. The instrument was face validated by three experts, two from business education and one from measurement of evaluation. A reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained which is high through test-retest method. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while t-test was used to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that each of the three strategies in the study, namely; teaching methods, teamwork and student study habits improves academic performance of business education students in business mathematics to a large extent. Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, it was recommended among others that business educators should teach business mathematics using simple to complex approach, involve students in group assignments and help students to develop effective personal study habits.

Keywords: *Academic performance, Business education, Business mathematics, Improvement*

Introduction

Business education is an aspect of vocational education which equips individuals with the

necessary theoretical knowledge and skills for effective performance in the business world either for paid job occupations or self-employment. Jim (2023) described business education as a systematic and organized programme of instruction aimed at transmitting business knowledge, skills, ideals, aptitude and technical know-how to recipients for usage in business offices and for teaching others. Business education programme is a specialized phase of vocational education that prepares beneficiaries to enter teaching and office occupations as capable and intelligent members of the labour force (Koko, 2013). In Nigerian tertiary institutions, the programme is currently offered under options, namely; accounting education, entrepreneurship education, marketing education and offices management technology. The primary objective of business education programme is to train ~~an~~ individuals to acquire skills and competencies for gainful employment in their professional areas (Osuala, 2009). The National Universities Commission which is the supervisory agency for university education in Nigeria, prepares the minimum standards to guide the universities for uniform operation in all fields of learning including Business Education in order to achieve the national policy on education. In Rivers State, there two state owned universities that offer business education programmes, namely: Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education both in Port-Harcourt. The department of Business education in these universities offers Business Mathematics as semester course (BED121 and BED 122) for all 100 level (year 1) students for all options. This is to help them acquire calculation skills required to work as ~~an~~ accountants, entrepreneurs and efficient business managers of business in an organization. Good academic performance in business mathematics is,

therefore, very important for the students to be able to meet up with the expectations of employers upon graduation. Over the years, Business Education students in these universities have persistently performed poorly in Business Mathematics. A close look at the academic performance of business education students in the course, Introduction to Mathematics, when compared to their mates in other fields of study and their performance in other courses like Introduction to Business, Principles of Vocational and Technical Education, among others indicates that their performance is very poor. This indicates that they are not being adequately equipped with the calculating/mathematics skills necessary to make them complete their programme and leave school as well-trained business education graduates. The question, therefore, becomes, what strategies are suitable for reversing the trend in order to improve the quality of graduates of Business Education from these universities? To what extent could teaching methods, team work and development of effective study habits contribute in improving the performance of Business Education students in Business Mathematics to help them possess a very high level of the required calculating and accounting skills for success in employment upon graduation? It is an established fact that effective teaching and learning which ensures good academic performance by students is a function of different factors. Atandi, Gisore & Ntabo, (2019) averred that teaching and learning effectiveness greatly depends on the method of teaching used by the teacher. Jalbrani (2014) stated that quality teaching is as a result of using students-centered method. This implies arranging students to study in teams which is considered very effective in helping all students in a class to learn. According to Inyang (2020), the essence of teaching at all level of education is to produce basic change

that facilitates good academic performance among learners and equips them with competencies for gainful employment upon graduation. In summary, teachers need to use appropriate methods of teaching in order to achieve the lesson objectives and good learning outcome while students need work together and assist each other for better understanding and especially, helping the slow learners.

Problem of the Study

Mathematics has been a difficult subject for many students in at all levels of education including the university. Many students have fear of courses involving Mathematics and calculation. Business education programme contains semester courses in Business Mathematics for all 100 level students irrespective of their options. Observations have shown that the academic performance of these students in the courses has been persistently low. This ugly situation implies that they are not being adequately equipped with the calculating/mathematics skills necessary to make them succeed in the business world as well-trained Business Education graduates. This could be as a result of teaching method adopted by the lecturers and/or the students' study habits. The problem of this study, therefore, is that the persistent poor academic performance in Business Mathematics among Business Education students in state-owned universities in Rivers State needs to be urgently reversed to ensure that the graduates have what it takes to succeed in employment. The extent teaching methods, team study among students and their study habits will solve this problem is not clearly known, hence, it is imperative to conduct this study to provide empirical data that will help relevant stakeholders take necessary actions.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to determine strategies for improving academic performance in Business Mathematics among Business Education students in state-owned universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the study determined the: The extent teaching methods will improve academic performance in Business Mathematics by Business Education students in state-owned universities in Rivers State.

Examine the extent to which team-work improve academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

1. Examine the extent to which study habit improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent will teaching method improve academic performance in Business Mathematics among Business Education students in Rivers state owned Universities in Rivers State?
2. To what extent will team-work improve academic performance of Business Education students in Rivers state owned universities?
3. To what extent will student study habit improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings on respondents from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent teaching methods will improve academic performance in Business Mathematics among

Business Education students in state-owned Universities in Rivers State.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings on respondents from Rivers state University and Ignatius Ajuru University of education on the extent to which team-work will improve academic performance in Business Mathematics among Business Education Students in state-owned Universities in Rivers State...

H03: there is no significant difference in the mean ratings on respondents from Rivers state University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education of educators on students study habit in Business Mathematics among Business Education Students in state-owned Universities in Rivers State.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted of all 39 business educators Business Educators in the two state-owned universities (30 from Rivers state university and 9 from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. There was no sampling because of the manageable size of the population. Structured questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. The instrument was face validated by three experts, two from Business Education and one from

Measurement and Evaluation their corrections and suggestions were affected by the researcher. The instrument was structured on a five point rating scale of: Very High Extent, High Extent, Moderate Extent, Low Extent, and Very Low Extent. Test re-test method was used to determine the internal consisting of the instrument and a reliability coefficient index of 0.79 was obtained. A total of 39 copies of Instrument were administered to the respondents and retrieved by the researcher. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions and determine the homogeneity of the respondents' mean ratings while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Decision for the research questions was based on the item and cluster mean scores in relation to the boundary limit of numbers on a five-point scale. A hypothesis is not rejected where the t-calculated value is less than t-table value, otherwise, it is rejected.

Results

Research question 1

To what extent does teaching method improve academic performance of Business Education students in Business Mathematics in Rivers state owned universities?

Table 1: Respondents mean ratings on the extent of teaching method improve academic performance of business education students in Business Mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

S/N	Item Statements	RSU			IAUE		
		Mean	SD	Remarks	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	Good teaching method motive student to learn business mathematics	4.20	0.57	High extent	4.01	0.59	High extent
2	Appropriate use of teaching method arose student interest in business mathematics	3.81	0.60	High extent	3.93	0.56	High extent

3	Effective use of teaching methods enhance students understanding of business mathematics topics	3.43	0.59	Moderate extent	3.85	0.57	High extent
4	Effective use of teaching methods encourages students to solve problems in mathematics	3.10	0.71	Moderate extent	3.10	0.70	moderate extent
5	Effective use of teaching methods increase students' academic performance in business mathematics	3.18	0.69	Moderate extent	2.90	0.73	Moderate extent
6	Effective use of teaching method helps to recall retained knowledge	3.72	0.62	High extent	3.83	0.58	High extent
7	Good use of teaching method enable some students to help and teach other students	2.80	0.82	Moderate extent	2.91	0.78	Moderate extent
8	effective use of teaching method increases students' academic performance in business mathematics	4.51	0.59	Very High extent	4.00	0.60	High extent
Grand mean		3.87			3.83		

Table 1 reveals that Business Educators in both Rivers state university and Ignatius Ajuru University of Educations agreed to all the items numbers1, 2, 3,4,5,6, and 8 to high extent and number 7 low extent. A pull grand mean value of 3.87 and 3.83, indicates high extent, which implies that teaching methods improves academic performance of

Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

Hypotheses 1: There is significant difference in the mean responses of Business Educators in RSU and IAUE on the extent to which teaching methods improves academic performance of Business Education student Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

Table 2: t-test comparison of the mean responses of Business Educators in RSU and IAUE on the extent to which teaching method improve academic performance of Business Education student in business mathematics.

Group	No	(x)	SD	df	t-cal	t-table	S/E	Decision
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RSU- Business Educators	30	3.75	0.65					
IAUE-Business Educators	9	3.83	0.61	37	0.083	1.96	0.89	Not Significant

Table 2, revealed that the calculated t-value of 0.083 less than t-table value of 1.96. It indicate that the null hypothesis shows no significance difference in the mean responses of Business Educators in RSU and IAUE on the extent to which teaching methods improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics.

Research question 2

To what extent does team-work improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

Table 2: respondents mean ratings on the extent of team-work improves academic performance of Business Education students in business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

S/N	Items statement	Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Team-work makes the members to participate actively in the subject matter to enhance academic performance.	4.30	0.58	High extent	4.10	0.62	High extent
2	Team-work sustains the interest of team members to improve academic performance.	4.14	0.63	High extent	3.84	0.65	High extent
3	Team-work helps to achieve the objective of the lesson towards improving academic performance.	4.32	0.61	High extent	4.12	0.67	High extent
4	Team-work provide good opportunities for slow learners to learn better and improve in their academic performance.	4.29	0.60	High extent	4.09	0.70	High extent
5	Team-work encourages fertilization of ideas for good academic performance	3.84	0.71	High extent	3.64	0.76	High extent
6	Team-work provide room for members to ask questions	3.30	0.74	Moderate extent	3.10	0.13	moderate extent
7	Team-work enhances understanding of difficult concept	4.12	0.76	High extent	3.92	0.71	High extent
Grand mean		4.04			3.83		

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

Table 2, shows that Business Educators agreed to the number 1 to 7, which indicates a common opinions. The pull grand mean value of 4.04 and 3.83 revealed that team work improves academic performance of Business Education students to high extent in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Educators in RSU and IAUE on the extent to which students’ team-work improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

Table 4: t-test comparison of the mean responses of business educators in RSU and IAUE on the extent team-work improves academic performance of Business Education students in business mathematics.

Group	No	(x)	SD	df	t-cal	t-table	S/E	Decision
RSU-Business Educators	30	4.04	0.66	37	0.701	1.96	0.781	Not Significant
IAUE- Business Educators	9	383	0.69					

Table 4, revealed that the calculated t-value of 0.701 was less than t-table value of 1.96. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Educators from the two universities on the extent to which team-work improves academic performance of Business

Education students in Business mathematics. Hence, the hypothesis was retained.

Research question 3

To what extent does students study habit improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities?

Table 5: Respondents mean ratings on the extent students’ study habit improves academic performance of Business Educations students in business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

S/N	Items statements	Mean ₁	SD	Remarks	Mean ₂	SD ₂	Remarks
1	Study habit sustains the students interest in the subject	3.80	0.62	High extent	3.51	0.68	High extent
2	Study habit motives students to learn easily and improve his/her academic performance.	3.61	0.68	High extent	3.14	0.71	Moderate extent
3	Good study habit of the students makes them contribute meaning fully during class work and assignment	3.02	0.72	Moderate extent	3.70	0.67	High extent

4	Study habit provides the student with opportunity of retention of knowledge for better academic performance.	3.10	0.70	Moderate extent	3.01	0.73	Moderate extent
5	Student that studies well perform better academically	4.21	0.57	High extent	4.11	0.56	High extent
6	Study habits permit the students to study at his/her own pace which improves academic performance	3.13	0.69	Moderate extent	3.00	0.65	Moderate extent
Grand mean		3.48			3.42		

Table 5, revealed that all Business Educators agreed to items numbers 1 to 6, which indicates a common opinion. The pull grand mean value of 3.48 and 3.42 implies that academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities was considered to a moderate extent. The standard deviation values ranging from 0.73 is a support to the opinions.

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business educators in RSU and IAUE on the extent to which students study habits improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics in Rivers state owned universities.

Table 6: t-test comparison of the mean responses of business educators in RSU and IAUE on the extent to which students study habits improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics.

Group	No	(x)	SD	df	t-cal	t-table	S/E	Decision
RSU-Business Educators	30	3.45	0.68					
IAUE-Business Educators	9	3.05	0.72	37	0.084	1.96	0.902	Not Significant

Result from Table 6, shows that, the calculated t-value of 0.084 was less than t-table value of 1.96, which indicates that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators on the extent student study habits improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics. Therefore the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Discussion

Findings of the study show that the respondents from the two universities rated teaching methods as a strategy that can improve academic performance of Business Education students of state-owned universities in Rivers State to a high extent This finding agrees with the findings of Atandi, Gisore and Ntabor (2019) that method of teaching is

responsible for effective teaching/learning to enhance academic performance of students. The researchers are with view that appropriate use of teaching methods by Business educators will greatly improve the academic performance of Business Education students of the institutions generally in all courses and particularly in Business Mathematics. The findings further revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of the respondents from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education on the extent teaching methods will improve Business Education students' academic performance in Business Mathematics. This implies that teaching methods is a suitable strategy for helping Business Education students acquire necessary calculation skills in Business Mathematics for success in employment as accounts, teachers or business managers. Findings from research question two, shows that team-work improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics to high extent in Rivers state owned universities. The researcher is with the view team-work and problem solving among the students improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics. The findings is in consonant with the findings of Nasmila and Rahman (2017) stated that applying group work improves students' achievements. The researcher is with the view that team work and problem solving among the students as encouraged by their lecturers enhances effective learning in Business mathematics course in Rivers state owned universities. The findings relating to research question three, showed that students' study habits improves academic performance of Business Education students in Business mathematics to a high extent in Rivers state owned universities. This findings was supported by the findings of Jafari,

Aghaei and Khatony (2019) which stated that study habits are important in predicting academic performance of students. The researchers are with opinion that well developed guided study habits of Business Education students improves their academic performance in business mathematics course in Rivers state owned universities. The analysis of the three null hypotheses revealed that the calculated t-values of 0.083, 0.701 and 0.084 are less than t-table value of 1.96. This indicates that, there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators from Rivers state university and Ignatius Ajuru University of education on the extent to which teaching methods, team-work among students and study habits improve academic performance of Business Educations students in Business mathematics.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that lecturers' use of appropriate teaching methods, team-work and development of good study habits among students are effective strategies for improving academic performance of Business Education students of state-owned universities in Rivers State in Business Mathematics in order to better equip them for employment success.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Business educators in Rivers state owned universities should teach Business mathematics course with simple to complex method to enhance good academic performance.
2. Business educators should introduce team-work or group assignment to students, this will encourage them to participate for better understanding of the subject matter.

3. Business Educators should guide the students on how to develop a personal study habits and study time table with follow-up measures.

REFERENCES

Atandi, B.C, Gizore, B.C & Ntabor, A.J. (2019). Influence of teaching method on students'academic performance in Kiswahili subject in public and private secondary school in Langiata sub-country. African research journal of education and social sciences. 6(2), 16-24.

Inyang, H. (2021). Impact of teaching methods on students' academic performance in biology in secondary schools. <https://harihryblogsport.com>.

Jalabani, L.N. (2014). The impact of effective teaching strategies on students' academic performance and learning outcome. <https://www.grun.com>.

Jim, E.U (2023). Constraints to effective utilization of electronic learning devices in teaching and Learning of Business Education courses in university in Rivers State RSU Journal of Education. 26(2), 77-83.

Jim, E.U. (2011). Utilization of e-learning for effective teaching of vocational education course in Nigeria tertiary institutions. Journal of research in science and technology education. 4(1), 41-47.

Nasimilah, N. & pahmen .A. (2017). Applying group work to improve students'grammar achievements. Imperial journal of inter

disciplinary research 3 (5), 1971-1975.
<http://www.infoguidenigeria.com>.

National University commission (2023). Core Curriculum and Minimum Academic Standards (CCMAS) for the Nigerian University system.

Osuala, E.C (2019). Foundation of Vocational Education. Cheston Agency Ltd.